

**PALIMPSESTOS CROMÁTICOS: UNA APROXIMACIÓN
AL TRASVASE DE LOS TÉRMINOS RELACIONADOS CON EL COLOR
EN LAS TRADUCCIONES AL ESPAÑOL Y AL RUMANO
DE “FAHRENHEIT 451” /**

**CHROMATIC PALIMPSESTS: AN APPROACH TO TRANSPOSING
COLOR TERMS VIA THE RENDITION OF FAHRENHEIT 451
INTO SPANISH AND ROMANIAN**

Lavinia IENCEANU, Assistant Professor, PhD
("Stefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, Romania)

lavinia.ienceanu@usm.ro, <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1343-410X>

Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 3, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

This research aims to trace the translational strategies employed by the Spanish and Romanian translators of *Fahrenheit 451* in rendering terms and collocations related to color. The major focus is on assessment of the degree of poetic resemblance, adjustment or deviation to or from the connotative load of the text under scrutiny. In addition, our contribution is also aimed at mapping the cultural shifts – if any – underlying the chromatic change induced by translatorial “infidelities”.